

The Taxonomic Report

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Notes on North American Butterflies. 1.

parts by

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ABSTRACT. New natural history elements and distribution records of several North American butterflies are reported. Taxonomy is often driven by geographical analyses. Cartography, coupled with internet-based imagery, opens up a promising wealth of information, allowing avocational researchers a tool by which inconvenient visits to institutional collections are no longer necessary for resolving some basic questions. While diversity and distribution of butterflies in North America are commonly believed to be fully known, the findings presented here show that much is yet to be learned of our butterfly fauna.

Rhode Island, USA Fall Butterfly Survey 2023

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ABSTRACT: The second TILS-sponsored survey to document butterflies near season's end in Rhode Island was conducted Sept. 16 to Oct. 14. The goal was to document southward migrants as well as northward migrants, and also the presence and abundance of resident late season broods in the Ocean State.

INTRODUCTION

Near the southern New England coast, cool evenings around the beginning of fall generally signal the start of the Monarch (*Danaus plexippus*) migration westward through Rhode Island and Connecticut, then south to the overwintering grounds in Mexico. While this migration is well documented, several other species have been observed to migrate with them. Past observations by the coordinator in 1983 and 1984 confirmed a steady movement of Question Marks (*Polygonia interrogationis*) along the same route, but in considerably smaller numbers. This movement may be more akin to a localized movement of individuals to more hospitable overwintering conditions, perhaps along the coast southward, rather than a true migration. Reports from nearby Massachusetts indicate a similar movement among Mourning Cloak (*Nymphalis antiopa*) butterflies, but not yet observed in Rhode Island. The Painted Lady (*Vanessa cardui*) and Common Buckeye (*Junonia coenia*) have been anecdotally reported to migrate southward in fall along the Atlantic coast but this has not yet been verified. Observations indicate that these two species do congregate in large numbers along the coast in early fall, but no actual movement has yet been observed in Rhode Island. Likely most of these will perish with the onset of winter. Interestingly, no Question Marks or Buckeyes, normally common in the fall, were reported in 2023.

Rhode Island, as well as the rest of the southern New England coastal region, is known for its comparatively moderated temperate climate, compared to inland areas. Rhode Island winters are often tempered by proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and Narragansett Bay, though extreme cold spells are not uncommon. The progression of spring is delayed by several days or weeks, due to the fact that the ocean remains cold for several months into seasonal warmup. Summers are generally cooler overall than interior

New England regions, and afternoon sea breezes are a welcome relief on summer days, often many miles inland. Fall sees the reverse of spring, with frosts and freezes delayed several weeks due to proximity to the ocean, which retains its warmth for several weeks into the fall. This extended mild, frost-free period allows continued migration of northbound migrants such as *Phoebis sennae* (Cloudless Sulphur), *Panoquina ocola* (Ocola Skipper) and *Hylephila phyleus* (Fiery Skipper) annually, as well as infrequent migrants such as *Danaus gilippus* (Queen) and *Dione vanillae* (Gulf Fritillary). It also provides continued safe passage for southbound migrants, among which *Danaus plexippus* (Monarch) is best known.

The 2023 count, spanning Sept. 16 to Oct. 15, experienced a very mild period, with only a slight, steady decline in daily temperatures. High temperatures in Providence ranged from 61-81°F (16-27°C) over the period. Nighttime temperatures varied considerably, but remained mild, well above frost temperatures, ranging from 46-70°F (8-21°C). Rain occurred infrequently during September, but most rains were light.

SOURCES AND METHODS

Butterflies were recorded primarily by cellphone camera or other photographic means. Sight reports without images were accepted from reliable sources. Records were submitted either directly to the coordinator (Harry Pavulaan) via email or Facebook Messenger, while others were obtained from internet sources: iNaturalist, e-Butterfly and the Rhode Island Butterflies and Moths Facebook group. Records are attributed to the list of contributors below. Many contributors to iNaturalist use made-up pseudonyms instead of their real names. Those not identified by real name are listed anonymously under “IN” (iNaturalist):

AB = Ann Buerry Brown	KT = Kerry Tehan
BT = Bill Thompson	LB = Lucille Boyce
DG = David Gregg	LY = Kevin Lynch via iNaturalist
DM = David Mozzoni via eButterfly	MI = Paul Miller
DS = Daniel Sullivan via iNaturalist	MN = Michael Newton
DT = Dee-Dee Taylor	NA = Jim Natale via iNaturalist
IN = iNaturalist – anonymous	PM = Pat Molloy
JN = Jacqui Bilodeau Nye	SD = Sue Dunn
JO = Jim O'Neill via iNaturalist	SF = Sandra Ferretti
JS = Jim Sweeney via iNaturalist	SG = Sandra Gaumont
KL = Karen Lee via iNaturalist	VM = Vanessa Massey
KM = Kent McFarland via iNaturalist, eButterfly	

RESULTS BY BUTTERFLY FAMILY

All butterflies are listed under their respective Lepidopteran FAMILY (i.e. Papilionidae). Butterflies are listed in the sequence given in the Pelham (2008) Catalogue. A comment, indicating residency or migratory status, is provided. Observations of larvae are listed separately, in alphabetic order by genus, regardless of Lepidopteran family group. All records are by city or town (underlined).

PAPILIONIDAE

***Papilio polyxenes* (Black Swallowtail)** – resident.

Narragansett: 18 Sept. (AB) **1** - Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

South Kingstown: 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **2**

***Pterourus glaucus glaucus* (Eastern Tiger Swallowtail)** – resident.

Warwick: 17 Sept. (SD) **1** - Nectaring on *Symphotrichum novi-belgii*.

***Pterourus troilus troilus* (Spicebush Swallowtail)** – resident.

Barrington: 4 Oct. (IN) **1** – Fresh individual, indicating partial third brood.
South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **1** - Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

PIERIDAE

***Pieris rapae* (Cabbage White)** – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **5** - Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).
Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **15**; 3 Oct. (PM) **10**
Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **4**; 2 Oct. (IN) **1**
East Providence: 17 Sept. (PM) **1**; 4 Oct. (PM) **10**; 13 Oct. (PM) **1**; 14 Oct. (PM) **1**
Jamestown: 5 Oct. (PM) **2**
Middletown: 6 Oct. (KM) **2**; 9 Oct. (DS) **1**; 9 Oct. (IN) **1**; 14 Oct. (KM) **8**
Narragansett: 20 Sept. (IN) **1**
Providence: 5 Oct. (KL) **1**
South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **1**; 20 Sept. (IN) **1**; Oct. 2 (IN) **1**; 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **47+**
Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1** – Nectaring on *Cichorium intybus* (Chicory).
Warwick: 14 Oct. (DM) **2**
Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **10**

***Colias eurytheme* (Orange Sulphur)** – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **2**
Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **8** - Nectaring on *Conoclinium coelstinum* (Ageratum); 3 Oct. (PM) **4**; 9 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Taraxacum officinale* (Dandelion).
Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **5**
East Providence: 4 Oct. (PM) **20**
Exeter: 9 Oct. (LB) **1** – Nectaring on *Phlox paniculata* (Summer Phlox).
Johnston: 7 Oct. (BT) **1**
North Kingstown: 19 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Zinnia* sp. (Zinnia).
South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **83**; Sept. 20 (IN) **1**; 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **5**
Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1**
Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **13**; 11 Oct. (JO) **1**

***Colias philodice* (Clouded Sulphur)** – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **4**
Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **10**
Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **3**
South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **10**; 17 Sept. (MN) **11**; 28 Sept. (IN) **1** - Nectaring on *Symphotrichum novae-angliae* (New England Aster).
Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1** – Nectaring on *Taraxacum officinale* (Dandelion)
Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **9**

***Phoebis sennae* (Cloudless Sulphur)** – seasonal migrant, occasionally breeding, perishing with onset of winter.

Narragansett: 2 Oct. (DG) **1**
Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **4** – 3 females ovipositing on *Senna marilandica*.

LYCAENIDAE

***Lycaena phlaeas hypophlaeas* (American Copper)** – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **15**
Bristol: 3 Oct. (PM) **15**
Cranston: 27 Sept. (JN) **4** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).
East Providence: 17 Sept. (VM) **1** - Nectaring on *Hylotelephium telephium* (Autumn Joy Sedum); 4 Oct. (PM) **10**
Pawtucket: 2 Oct. (IN) **1**
Portsmouth: 12 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Hylotelephium spectabile* (Autumn Joy Stonecrop).
North Kingstown: 8 Oct. (MI) **1** – Nectaring on *Rudbeckia hirta* (Black Eyed Susan).

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **10**; Oct. 2 (IN) **1**

Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1**

Warwick: 14 Oct. (DM) **2**

Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **4**

***Calycopsis cecrops* (Red Banded Hairstreak)** – resident.

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **2** - Nectaring on *Conoclinium coelstinum* (Ageratum).

***Strymon melinus* (Gray Hairstreak)** – resident.

North Kingstown: 20 Sept. (MI) **1**

Lincoln: 10 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Cupido comyntas comyntas* (Eastern Tailed Blue)** – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **1**; 17 Sept. (MN) **5**

Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **5**

***Celastrina neglecta* (Summer Azure)** – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **1**

NYMPHALIDAE

***Danaus plexippus* (Monarch)** – seasonal migrant, mass southbound movement in fall.

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **3**

Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **3**

East Providence: 4 Oct. (PM) **1**

Little Compton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1**

Middletown: 3 Oct. (LY) **1** Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod); 6 Oct. (KM) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Narragansett: 20 Sept. (IN) **1**; 21 Sept. (IN) **17**; 3 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Providence: 19 Sept. (SD) **2**; 6 Oct. (KT) – Nectaring on *Buddleia* (Butterfly Bush).

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **3**; 17 Sept. (MN) **12**; 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **1**; 3 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Nipponanthemum nipponicum* (Nippon or Montauk Daisy).

Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1**

Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **6**; 5 Oct. (DT) **1**

***Phyciodes tharos tharos* (Pearl Crescent)** – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **2**

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **3**

Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **7**

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **4**

***Polygonia comma* (Eastern Comma)** – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **1**

***Vanessa virginiensis* (American Lady)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **1** - Nectaring on *Cirsium* sp. (Thistle).

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **2**

Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **3**

Cranston: 22 Sept. (JN) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush).

East Providence: 17 Sept. (PM) **1**

Foster: 12 Oct. (IN) **1** - Nectaring on *Zinnia* sp. (Zinnia)

Middletown: 3 Oct. (LY) **1** Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

South Kingstown: 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **2**

Warwick: 14 Oct. (DM) **1**

Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **2**; 13 Oct. (NA) **1** - Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. purple var. (Butterfly Bush).

***Vanessa atalanta* (Red Admiral)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Jamestown: 5 Oct. (PM) **1**

***Limenitis archippus archippus* (Viceroy)** – resident.

Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **2**

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **2**

Lethe appalachia appalachia (**Appalachian Brown**) – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **1**

Cercyonis pegala alope (**Common Wood Nymph**) – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (MN) **2**

HESPERIIDAE

Atalopedes huron (**Eastern Sachem**) – resident.

Barrington: 21 Sept. (PM) **1**

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **20+** – Nectaring on *Conoclinium coelstinum* (Ageratum), *Verbena bonariensis* (Purpletop Vervain),
Zinnia sp. (*Zinnia*); 3 Oct. (PM) **7**

Charlestown: 17 Sept. (MN) **50+**

East Providence: 17 Sept. (PM) **1** - Nectaring on *Buddleia*.

Jamestown: 17 Sept. (SF) **2**

Little Compton: 21 Sept. (JS) **1**

Narragansett: 20 Sept. (IN) **1**

North Kingstown: 19 Sept. (IN) **2** – Nectaring on *Celosia cristata* (Cockscomb), *Symphotrichum novae-angliae* (New
England Aster).

Providence: 19 Sept. (SD) **1**

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **3**; 17 Sept. (MN) **50+**; 3 Oct. (PM, SG) – “too many to count” +7

Tiverton: 21 Sept. (JS) **2**

Westerly: 17 Sept. (MN) **80+**

Polites themistocles themistocles (**Tawny-edged Skipper**)

Bristol: 22 Sept. (PM) **4** (R.I. late record) - Nectaring on *Conoclinium coelstinum* (Ageratum), *Centaurea stoebe* (Spotted
Knapweed).

South Kingstown: 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **2**

Ancyloxypha numitor (**Least Skipper**) – resident.

South Kingstown: 17 Sept. (DG) **2**

Panoquina ocola (**Ocola Skipper**) – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

South Kingstown: 3 Oct. (PM, SG) **1**

CATERPILLARS

Papilio polyxenes (**Black Swallowtail**) – resident.

Bristol: 8 Oct. (IN) **1** – Caterpillar on unidentified host.

Pterourus troilus troilus (**Spicebush Swallowtail**) – resident.

Coventry: 17 Sept. (MS) **3** - Caterpillars on *Lindera benzoin* (Spicebush) and *Sassafras albidum* (Sassafras).

Danaus plexippus (**Monarch**) – seasonal migrant, mass southbound movement in fall.

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (IN) **1** – Caterpillar on *Asclepias* sp. (Milkweed).

Vanessa virginiensis (**American Lady**) – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Charlestown: 3 Oct. (IN) **1** – Caterpillar on *Aletris fainosa* (Colicroot).
